

As on 12-02-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended in order to add record of crops season, ecological requirement and tolerance into the knowledge base system. There are three tables involved; i) Season, ii) Agroecology and iii) Tolerance.

i) Season

Steps for data collection (season length of the crop):

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning the potential yield of the crops. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The keyword often used to search in the search engine is “scientific name + season”.
3. Often in the source, the season is directly mentioned by how long it takes for the crop to be harvested after the sowing/planting is done. The data presented this way is most likely meant for the annual crops. However, for the perennial crops (especially for the fruit harvest), the season length is likely to be presented as the duration taken from one harvest to its next harvest.
4. In the source, the lowest value will be recorded as minimum value while the highest as the maximum value.
5. In some cases, gap-filling can be done where the data of a crop can be recorded to other in assumption that they could be the same; however, the record strictly requires an indication that the data is estimated through gap-filling method. ‘Data Flag’ is the field to indicate this process.
6. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, knowledge capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry in ‘**Season**’ table:

1. There are 13 fields to be entered, five of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name selection in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Location (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the specific location of the crops being grown. Location **MUST** be recorded as stated on the data source.
- If there is no specific location stated in the data source, location should be entered **GLOBAL**.

1.3 Season Length (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the minimum and maximum period length (days) when crops grow successfully in a year. Choose the lowest value as ‘Minimum’ and highest as ‘Maximum’.

- The length of a growing season may vary from place to place. If there is more than one location stated in data source, one **MUST** create a new record according to its location.

1.4 Data Flag

- The data flag is given to indicate the methodology used to derive the value.
- In the database the field will show a drop-down menu for selection. The selection is fixed as below:
 - i) Analytical value - Value of analysed result which is directly taken from the source.
 - ii) Calculated value - Value derived from a source or multiple sources which are aggregated and processed into one calculated value OR value is calculated for unit conversion.
 - iii) Roundup value - Value is being rounded e.g. 2545 -> 2500.
 - iv) Estimated value - Value is estimated from the source hints.
 - v) Gapfilled value - Value meant for a crop is derived from the values of its closest relative or species.
 - vii) Source presented value - Value presented in the source.
 - viii) Under revision - Value meant to be revised.

1.5 Period Sowing to 1st Harvest

- This is referring to the minimum and maximum period length from sowing to the first harvest in days. Choose the lowest value as 'Minimum' and highest value as 'Maximum'.
- This field is meant for a crop that is propagated using seed.

1.6 Period Propagating to 1st Harvest

- This is referring to the minimum and maximum period length from propagating vegetative parts of plants to the first harvest in days. Choose the lowest value as 'Minimum' and highest as 'Maximum'.
- This field is meant for a crop that is propagated through vegetative parts instead of using seed (including grafting).

1.7 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.

1.8 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

ii) Agroecology

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning the potential yield of the crops. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The keyword often used to search in the search engine is “scientific name + 'variable name’”. The keywords for the variable names that are commonly used; temperature, rainfall and soil with an additional keyword of “requirement”.
3. In the source, the lowest value will be recorded as minimum value while the highest as the maximum value. If the mean is not provided, the average of both values will be calculated. The lowest and the highest values may derive from different sources but to be compiled in a single record of a single crop.
4. If the multiple values are presented, the average of all the values will be calculated. This is usually be the case when the source presents abundant values of the variables which are coming from multiple crop variants.
5. In some cases, gap-filling can be done where the data of a crop can be recorded to other in assumption that they could be the same; however, the record strictly requires an indication that the data is estimated through gap-filling method. ‘Data Flag’ is the field to indicate this process.
6. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, knowledge capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry in ‘**Agroecology**’ table:

1. There are 98 fields to be entered, two of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Ensure there is **NO** previous record which has used the same crop.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name selection in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Zone

- Referring to the world climate classification. The classification is divided into five zones according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification which are:
 - i) Zone A: Tropical/megathermal climates
 - ii) Zone B: Dry (arid and semiarid) climates
 - iii) Zone C: Temperate/mesothermal climates
 - iv) Zone D: Continental/microthermal climates
 - v) Zone E: Polar and alpine climates
- In the database, this field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes, which means the zone is related to the crop and leave it empty if the answer is no, which is if the zone is unrelated to the crop.
- User may select more than one classification if it is stated on data source.

1.3 Climate Zone

- This field refers to the description of the climate zone in which the crop is suitable to be grown e.g. tropical wet (Ar), tropical wet and dry (Aw), etc.

1.4 Altitude

- 'Altitude Optimal' refers to the point above the sea level up to where the crop could grow the best.
- 'Altitude Absolute' refers to the point above the sea level up to where the crop could grow.
- Choose the lowest point as 'Min' and highest as 'Max'. Mean value may be calculated through the value from 'Max' and 'Min' point.
- Point **MUST** be recorded in metre (m) unit.

1.5 Latitude

- 'Latitude Optimal' refers to the measurement of distance north or south of the Equator in which crop could grow the best.
- 'Latitude Absolute' refers to the measurement of distance north or south of the Equator in which crop could survive.
- This field comprises 'Maximum', 'Mean' and 'Minimum' point. Maximum latitude is the highest latitude point up to the north and minimum point is the lowest latitude point down to the south.

1.6 Light Intensity

- 'Light Intensity Optimal' refers to the level of light intensity at which crop could grow the best.
- 'Light Intensity Absolute' refers to the level of light intensity at which crop could grow.
- In the database, the level is entered in text and **MUST NOT MORE** than 100 words. Choose the lowest level as 'Minimum', the highest as 'Maximum' and moderate level as 'Mean'

1.7 Optimal Aspect

- This field refers to the compass direction of slope (if there is a slope) e.g. southernly.
- Aspect unit is the compass point, which can be expressed as NW, WSW, etc., or degrees, e.g. N is 0 or 360°, S is 180°, etc.

1.8 Optimal Slope

- Referring to the maximum, minimum and mean slope value/ratio at which crop could grow the best.
- Topography = measurement of elevation; Slope = % change in elevation over a distance

1.9 Photoperiod

- 'Photoperiod Long' refers to the crop that needs long-daylight duration (more than 14 hours) to start flowering.

- 'Photoperiod Neutral' refers to the crop that does not need specific light duration to flower (can initiate flower over a wide range of photoperiods)'.
 - 'Photoperiod Short' refers to the crop that needs a short-day light duration (less than 12 hours) to start flowering.
 - In the database, this field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

2.0 Production System

- The description of the system used to produce this crop e.g. monocropping

2.1 Rainfall

- 'Rainfall Optimal' refers to the rainfall requirement at which the crop could grow the best in a year.
- 'Rainfall Absolute' refers to the rainfall requirement at which the crop could grow in a year.
- This field comprises 'Maximum', 'Mean' and 'Minimum' value of rainfall and **MUST** be recorded in millimeter (mm). Mean value could be derived from maximum and minimum value of the rainfall in a year.
- Value given in the data source could be presented in the form of range, user can enter the lowest value as minimum, and the highest value as maximum.
- The maximum, minimum and mean value could be collected from different sources in one crop record.

2.2 Heavy Metal Toxicity

- 'Heavy metal Toxicity Optimal' refers to if the plant is vulnerable to high/moderate/low level of soil toxicity in optimal growth condition.
- 'Heavy metal Toxicity Absolute' refers to if the plant is vulnerable to high/moderate/low level of soil toxicity to grow.
- In the database, this field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

2.3 Soil Depth

- 'Soil Depth Optimal' refers to the distance at which crop is planted from the soil surface to the rootball or root flare that is required for the crop to grow the best.
- 'Soil Depth Absolute' refers to the distance at which crop is planted from the soil surface to the rootball or root flare that is required for the crop to live.
- Soil depth optimal and absolute comprises three different distance which are:
 - i) Deep - Distance is more than 150 cm
 - ii) Medium - Distance is from 50 – 150 cm
 - iii) Low - Distance is less than 50 cm
- In the database, this field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

2.4 Soil Fertility

- Referring to plant requirements of high/moderate/low level of soil fertility under optimal and absolute level. Soil fertility is the capacity to receive, store and transmit energy to support plant growth.
- This field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

2.5 Soil pH

- This field is to record the pH value in soil that is required for the crop to grow.
- It comprises an optimal level (level at which the crop is best grown) and absolute level (level at which the crop could grow).
- Value is recorded according to maximum, mean and minimum value. Mean value could be calculated from the maximum and minimum pH value.

2.6 Soil Salinity

- Referring to the salt concentration in the soil.
- Soil salinity optimal and absolute comprises three different level which are:
 - i) High - Soil salinity is more than 10 dS/m
 - ii) Medium - Soil salinity is between 4-10 dS/m
 - iii) Low - Soil salinity is less than 4 dS/m
- This field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

2.7 Soil Texture

- 'Soil Texture Optimal' comprises three different level which are:
 - i) Heavy - Crop could grow the best in silty clay, sandy clay, clay
 - ii) Medium - Crop could grow the best in sandy loams, loams, sandy clay loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam, silty clay loam
 - iii) Light - Crop could grow the best in sands and loamy sands
- 'Soil Texture Absolute' also comprises three different level which are:
 - i) Heavy - Crop could live in silty clay, sandy clay, clay
 - ii) Medium - Crop could live in sandy loams, loams, sandy clay loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam, silty clay loam
 - iii) Light - Crop could live in sands and loamy sands
- This field is shown in the form of YES or NO selection. User **MUST** tick the column if the answer is yes and leave it empty if the answer is no.

2.8 Temperature

- 'Temperature Optimal' refers to the temperature at which the crop could grow the best.
- 'Temperature Absolute' refers to the temperature at which the crop could grow
- This field comprises 'Maximum', 'Mean' and 'Minimum' value and **MUST** be recorded in Degree Celsius. Mean value could be derived from maximum and minimum value.
- Value given in the data source could be presented in the form of range, user can enter the lowest value as minimum, and the highest value as maximum.

- The maximum, minimum and mean value could be collected from different sources in one crop record.

2.9 Texture

- Texture indicates the relative content (in percentage) of particles of various sizes, such as sand, silt and clay in the soil.
- It comprises three categories which are:
 - i) Texture Clay: Percentage of clay in which crop could grow the best
 - ii) Texture Sand: Percentage of sand in which crop could grow the best.
 - iii) Texture Silt: Percentage of silt in which crop could grow the best.
- The value is recorded in percentage.

3.0 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the ecological requirement of the crop itself.

3.1 Metadata (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

References:

- National Geographic Society (2020). Latitude. Retrieved from <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/latitude/>
- Climate Change & Infectious Diseases Group (2019). World Maps of Koppen-Geiger Climate Classification. Retrieved from <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation (2020). Nutrients and soil fertility management. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/tc/exact/sustainable-agriculture-platform-pilot-website/nutrients-and-soil-fertility-management/en/>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation (2020). Soil Texture. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/tempref/FI/CDrom/FAO_Training/FAO_Training/General/x6706e/.!53884!x6706e06.htm

iii) Tolerance

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning the potential yield of the crops. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The keyword often used to search in the search engine is “scientific name + 'tolerance attribute' + tolerance”. The keywords for the tolerance attribute that are commonly used; drought, salinity, acidity, frost etc.
3. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, knowledge capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry in '**Tolerance**' table:

2. There are three fields to be entered, two of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name selection in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Crop Tolerance

- This field is to store information on the ability of the crop to withstand biotic or abiotic stress e.g. drought, high salinity, high temperature, pest, disease, etc.
- The information is stored in an open-ended text.

1.3 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.